

minasargyou@outlook.com

From: HackerOne <no-reply@hackerone.com>
Sent: Thursday, 22 December, 2022 17:21
To: minasargyou@outlook.com
Subject: Claim your report for ICANN on HackerOne

You have submitted a report for [ICANN](#) on HackerOne. Claim this report so you can continue participating in their program and be listed in their [hall of fame](#). Just click below to get started.

REDACTED

If you believe you are not the intended recipient of this email, please contact support@hackerone.com.

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minasargyrou@outlook.com

From: Minas Argyrou
Sent: Monday, 8 May, 2023 21:42
To: vulnerability@icann.org; iana@iana.org
Subject: OID Takeover due to IANA PEN Modification Request Incorrect Verification
Signed By: minasargyrou@outlook.com

Importance: High

Hello,

On 20221222, I have reported a Vulnerability through your form on HackerOne (<https://hackerone.com/icann>). HackerOne sent me a confirmation e-mail message that your Security Team has received the Report. There has been no further communication from you or HackerOne. Since the Security Team did not communicate back, the provision for "mutual agreement" on a disclosure timeline/timeframe and the "Last Resort" clause of having to wait for 180days before publishing do not apply. Lastly, I am not a member of the Private Program.

I am informing you of publication on Zenodo and ResearchGate:

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7905552](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7905552)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7905552>

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/370593769_OID_Takeover_due_to_IANA_PEN_Modification_Request_Incorrect_Verification

Sincerely,
Argyrou Minas